

PHRAZEOLGY IN ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10197081>

Abstract. Phraseologism is an integral and organic part of both the language system and culture. It is also called a phraseological turnover, a speech turnover - this is a stable combination of words characteristic only of a given language, the meaning of which is not determined by the meaning of the words included in it, taken separately. That is, words that are part of phraseological units more or less lose their own lexical meaning. Thus, the phraseological unit is used as a whole, ready-made phrase. The combination of the meanings of the words included in it is the lexical meaning of the entire phraseological unit. The following article is devoted to the role of phraseology in the English language.

Key words: phrase, idiom, word combination, speech, synonym, colloquial phraseology.

ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЯ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. Фразеологизм является неотъемлемой и органичной частью как языковой системы, так и культуры. Его еще называют фразеологическим оборотом, речевым оборотом - это устойчивое сочетание слов, характерное только для данного языка, значение которого не определяется значением входящих в него слов, взятых отдельно. То есть слова, входящие в состав фразеологизмов, в большей или меньшей степени теряют собственное лексическое значение. Таким образом, фразеологизм используется как цельное, готовое словосочетание. Совокупность значений входящих в него слов и есть лексическое значение всего фразеологизма. Следующая статья посвящена роли фразеологизма в английском языке.

Ключевые слова: словосочетание, идиома, словосочетание-комбинация, речь, синоним, разговорная фразеология.

Phraseological units include phrases of the following types: idioms, collocations, proverbs, sayings, grammatical phraseological units, phraseological schemes. The world of English

phraseology is large and diverse. Every aspect of his research certainly deserves the attention it deserves.

Classification of phraseological units of the English language Structural classification A. Substantive phraseological units. Phraseologisms that are functionally related to a noun are considered to be substantive. That is, the core component of substantive phraseological units is a noun. For example: a drop in the bucket (drop in the bucket); Box and Cox (alternating); wind bag (philosopher; battle-ax, etc. B. Verb phrases Phraseologisms, functionally correlated with a verb, should be considered verbal. That is, the core component of such phraseological units is the verb. For example: to play it cool (behave calmly, coolly); to talk big (boast); to break a bubble (expose the true face); to be in the pot (drunk); to make mountains of mokehills (much ado about nothing), etc. C. Adjective phraseological units Adjective should be considered phraseological units, functionally correlated with adjectives, that is, phraseological units, the core component of which is the adjective. The share of adjective in the total volume of the studied phraseological units is very insignificant. D. Phraseologisms with sentence structure In the English language there are phraseological units that are structurally related to the sentence. Typical are those phraseological units built according to the structure of a simple sentence and having components that are related as subject and predicate. For example: he has no guts (he is a worthless person, he is worthless); you said it (I totally agree with you); you're telling me (you're telling me! I don't know!); It never rains but pours (Trouble does not come alone); wipe it off (stop laughing, enough jokes); never say die (don't hang your nose); sink or swin (everything is at stake, there is no choice), etc. English aphorisms and proverbs belong to this subgroup of phraseological units. Their number is great.

Speech is the main way people interact. To convey the meaning of the topic of conversation, mood, attitude to certain circumstances, quotes are used that are relevant in a particular situation, proverbs and sayings, phraseological units. The use of figurative expressions distinguishes a broadminded person who thinks outside the box and has a certain store of knowledge. Phraseologisms are divided into several categories: Phraseological unity (idioms) is a speech turnover, the meaning of which does not correspond to the meaning of the words used: a bull in a china shop - an elephant in a china shop. By itself, this expression does not mean anything, but in context it can be characterized by an awkward person. Phraseological combinations are expressions in which one word is used freely, and the second is associated with the first: a bosom friend is a bosom friend. The word "friend" is widely used, and only in combination with it is the word "bosom" used. Phraseological expressions are ready-made speech phrases that consist of words with a free meaning, they practically do not resemble phraseological units. At the same

time, like the previous categories of phraseological units, they are always used accurately and without using any synonyms: live and learn - live and learn. The English language has a thousand-year history. During this time, a large number of expressions have accumulated in it, which people have found successful, well-aimed and beautiful. So a special layer of the language arose - phraseology, a set of stable expressions that have independent meaning. Learning English is widespread in our country. Good knowledge of the language, including English, is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Knowledge of phraseology makes it extremely easy to read both journalistic and fiction literature. Reasonable use of phraseological units makes speech more idiomatic. With the help of phraseological expressions that are not translated literally, but are perceived rethinking, the aesthetic aspect of the language is enhanced. "With the help of idioms, as with the help of different shades of colors, the information aspect of the language is complemented by a sensory-intuitive description of our world, our life." The world of modern English phraseology is large and diverse, and every aspect of its study certainly deserves due attention. English phraseology is distinguished by a wealth of functional-style and emotionally-expressive synonyms. The stylistic coloring of phraseological units, like words, determines their consolidation in a certain style of speech. At the same time, two groups of phraseological units are distinguished in the composition of phraseology: common phraseological units that do not have a permanent connection with one or another functional style and functionally fixed phraseological units. The former include, for example, the following: Fromtimetotime - from time to time Farandaway - much. They find application both in books and in colloquial speech. Unlike common vocabulary, which represents a very significant part of the English language and vocabulary, common phraseology, in terms of the number of units, occupies a modest place in the entire mass of English phraseological units. Functionally fixed phraseological units are stylistically heterogeneous: their paradigms differ in the degree of expressiveness, expressiveness of emotional properties

The phraseological units belonging to it are often given in explanatory dictionaries without stylistic marks, however, they still stand out against the background of common phraseological units with a bright colloquial color, a slightly reduced, familiar tone in sound. Colloquial phraseological units, as a rule, are figurative, which gives them a special expression, liveliness, brightness. Colloquial phraseology, generally close to colloquial, is distinguished by a greater decline. Rough colloquial phraseology sounds even sharper. It includes abusive stable combinations that represent a gross violation of the language norm. Another stylistic layer is formed by book phraseology. It is used in functional book styles, mainly in writing. As part of

book phraseology, a scientific one stands out, which is a composite of terms: center of gravity
center of gravity thyroid gland thyroid gland school-leaving certificate publicist school-leaving
certificate people of good will people of goodwill formal business take place to take place

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